

INTELLIGENT CURE PROCESSING OF PMR-15

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ABSTRACT

An intelligent, closed-loop expert system has been developed for PMR-15. It has been used for intelligent, automated sensor/model control of the fabrication of flat PMR-15 graphite panels in both the autoclave and the thermal press. Various freezer aged prepreg samples exhibiting significantly different processing properties as a result of the aging process have been used. This expert system uses in-situ Frequency Dependent Electromagnetic Sensing (FDEMS), the Loos processing model, and the Qualitative Processing Automation Language (QPAL) software shell developed by Frances Abrams in conjunction with the Universal Technology Corporation for the United States Air Force.

The Loos model predicts and optimizes the PMR-15 cure process prior to actual panel fabrication. This includes the time-temperature dependence of the extent of reaction, flow, and part consolidation. The FDEMS sensing system monitors in-situ the removal of solvent, changes in viscosity and temperature, reaction advancement, and completion of cure continuously throughout the fabrication process. The real-time sensor data is compared with the optimum processing conditions determined by the Loos processing model.

The QPAL component of the expert system reduces the total cure process to a series of discrete processing subtasks. Each episode compares the actual state of the curing resin with the 'ideal' cure goals determined through prior experimentation and use of the Loos processing model. It provides a language for making decisions on subsequent adjustments to the temperature and the pressure controllers of the press or autoclave, based on the achievement or the avoidance of specific processing goals during the fabrication process. The new process control setpoints are sent via the FDEMS interface to the press or autoclave controller. The use of this intelligent, automated sensor-model system to optimize and to control the cure process of fresh and aged PMR-15 prepreg will be discussed.

Key Words: Intelligent Process Control, Modelling, Sensors, Composites

1. INTRODUCTION

Significant progress in successfully adjusting to the wide variation in run to run PMR-15/graphite composite processing properties has been made. By using the intelligent automated sensor-model cure control system developed at William and Mary, we have successfully controlled the cure of variously aged batches of PMR-15 prepreg. This expert system couples the power of in situ Frequency Dependent Electromagnetic Sensing (FDEMS) measurements with the deductive capabilities of the Qualitative Process Automation Language (QPAL) PMR-15 specific knowledge base containing the process goals created from the results of the Loos processing model, manufacturer recommendation and prior experimentation. By monitoring and evaluating the changing resin state as it cures, real-time adjustments are made to the remainder

of the cure process. Thus a wide range of parameters, including variations in tool temperature and pressure and in the prepreg as a result of resin batch variation, moisture uptake, out time during part preparation and advancement in resin degree of cure may be taken into account.

Conventionally formulated PMR-15 is a stoichiometric mixture of the monomers 5-norbornene-2,3-dicarboxylate (NE), dimethyl 3,3',4,4'-benzophenone tetracarboxylate (BTDE) and 4,4'-methylenedianiline (MDA) in the ratio 2(NE):(n+1)MDA:n(BTDE) where $n = 2.087$ (1-8). Previously we have discussed the variations in actual resin samples as a function of incidental hydrolysis, esterification, and oligomer formation (9-11) and the results of our initial work on intelligently controlling the cure of PMR-15 based composites (12).

Gluyas (13), Kranbuehl (9-11, 14-15) and others (16,17) have shown that in situ dielectric measurements provide a convenient method for monitoring the complete cure of PMR-15 (and other matrix resin systems). This report focuses on the FDEMS-QPAL intelligent cure control system's responses to variations in the PMR-15 matrix resin as a function of prepreg storage time under freezer conditions.

2. FDEMS THEORY

Measurements are made of the capacitance, C , and conductance, G , using the Dek Dyne microsensor. The complex permittivity $\epsilon^* = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''$ was calculated from $\epsilon' = C \text{ material}/C_0$ and $\epsilon'' = G \text{ material}/C_0 2\pi f$ where f is the frequency of applied electric field. This calculation is possible when using the Dek Dyne sensor whose geometry independent capacitance, C_0 , is invariant over all measurement conditions.

Both the real and the imaginary parts of ϵ^* have an ionic and dipolar component. The dipolar component arises from diffusion of bound charge or molecular dipole moments and is generally the major component of the dielectric signal at high frequencies and in highly viscous media. The ionic component often dominates ϵ^* at low frequencies, low viscosities and/or higher temperatures.

3. QUALITATIVE PROCESS AUTOMATION LANGUAGE (QPAL)

QPAL, developed cooperatively by Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio, and the Universal Technology Corporation, Dayton, Ohio, is a highly structured Macintosh™ programming language that has been tailored for polymer cure processing. The use of QPAL in an expert control system provides three distinct advantages. First, complicated, and often conflicting, goals for the composite fabrication process are reduced to a series of discrete steps, or episodes, which define the desired cure process. Another advantage is the portability of a given resin specific knowledge base, with minor modifications, to other expert control systems also using QPAL. Finally, QPAL is capable of testing a newly modified knowledge base either internally through a user defined trace or externally from previously obtained experimental FDEMS/temperature data without having to run a series of time consuming and expensive composite fabrication runs (12).

4. EXPERIMENTAL

PMR-15/graphite prepreg, provided by ICI Fiberite, has been used to make flat composite panels ranging in thicknesses of less than 1/8 inch to 1/4 inch. Various prepreg samples have been used, ranging in age from fresh to one year old under everyday freezer storage conditions.

FDEMS measurements are made over the range of frequencies from 125 Hz to 1 MHz using a Dek Dyne FDEMS microsensor. The microsensor consists of a fine array of two interdigitated comb electrodes on a ceramic substrate. It is inert, disposable, planar, and geometry independent. The sensor is constructed of noble metals and high temperature ceramics and contains no solid state circuitry which is vulnerable to harsh processing environments. The sensor can withstand the oxidative conditions and tool temperature and pressures for cure conditions exceeding 400°C and 1 MPa. This single disposable sensor monitors simultaneously the entire range in magnitude (usually 10^2 to 10^8) of both the real ϵ' and imaginary ϵ''

components of the permittivity continuously throughout the entire cure process.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the FDEMS output for a "typical" fresh PMR-15 prepreg (ICI Lot #10502S) cure using a time-temperature profile that incorporates the results of our previous work. Region A shows FDEMS sensor wet-out on a slow 2°C/minute ramp to 80°C and the achievement of a viscosity minimum for the system. Region B is a one hour hold at 80°C to allow for solvent elution and maximum part wet-out. Region C shows the onset of imidization as characterized by a drop of over four decades in the ionic mobility, the $\epsilon'' \cdot \omega$ overlapping lines, and thereby the drop in resin fluidity. Region D shows the continuation of the imidization reaction during a one hour hold at 200°C. Normally one would want to hold until the imidization is complete as evidenced by the decrease in the slope of the FDEMS signal; that is, $((d\epsilon''/dt)/\epsilon'')$ approaching zero. Here we see that the use of sensor feedback would have shown the imidization reaction to be incomplete and therefore the hold would have been extended by the intelligent, automated cure control system. Regions E and F show the viscosity minimum achieved during a ramp to ca. 265°C and the subsequent decrease in FDEMS signal as residual solvent and other volatiles are eluted during the hold. Finally, Regions G and H show the ramp to and hold at 320°C, the final crosslinking hold. Note that after approximately 75 minutes in the 320°C hold the change in slope of ϵ'' , $((d\epsilon''/dt)/\epsilon'')$, is small and close to zero, and "full cure" based on user criteria is reached. Had our intelligent, automated cure control system controlled this run using the criterion of $((d\epsilon''/dt)/\epsilon'') \leq 3.0 \times 10^{-5}$, it could have terminated the run after a total cure time of 375 minutes, thus saving 105 minutes of the 480 minutes shown here.

Figure 2 shows the dielectric/temperature data collected for the intelligent, sensor-model automated cure of fresh PMR-15 prepreg (ICI Lot #11769S). Region A shows the panel warming from room temperature to ca. 80°C. FDEMS sensor wet out as the resin reaches its ultimate viscosity minimum is indicated by the sharp increase in the $\text{Log}(\epsilon'' \cdot \omega)$ signal at 81°C. Region B, Imidization Onset, is a hold near 80°C allowing for solvent elution. Here Region B is actually a continuation of the ramp due to thermal lag as the part reaches the intelligently determined hold temperature set point. The cure episode terminates after 14 minutes when the criteria that the magnitudes of $\text{Log}(\epsilon'' \cdot \omega)$ at 500 Hz, 5 kHz and 25 kHz are less than 8.0 for four consecutive readings, that the change in the 25 kHz FDEMS signal, $((d\epsilon''/dt)/\epsilon'')$, is decreasing for four consecutive cycles, and that the magnitude of $\text{Log}(\epsilon'' \cdot \omega)$ at 25 kHz decreases by 10% from the maximum value determined at the beginning of the hold are met. Region C shows the 2-3°C per minute ramp to 200°C. Region D is the Imidization Hold and is characterized by a steady drop in FDEMS signal as the imidization reaction progresses. The data meets the user-defined termination criterion that the magnitude of $((d\epsilon''/dt)/\epsilon'')$ at 25 kHz be less than 3×10^{-4} for four consecutive data acquisition cycles after 105 minutes. Region E shows the determination of the Crosslinking Minimum Viscosity temperature at 235°C, based on the "folding over", or decrease, in the rate of increase of the dielectric signal. Note that this temperature is thirty degrees lower than the model-based 265°C "ideal" for PMR-15. After 28 minutes in Region F, the Crosslinking Hold, $((d\epsilon''/dt)/\epsilon'')$ at 25 kHz was less than 3×10^{-4} for four consecutive FDEMS readings, meeting the knowledge base termination criterion. Region G shows the slow 2°C per minute ramp to 320°C and Region H shows the Final Cure Hold at 320°C to complete the crosslinking reaction. In this run, the final episode ended after a maximum allowed time of 240 minutes because the magnitude change in the 25 kHz dielectric signal $((d\epsilon''/dt)/\epsilon'')$ did not meet the required criterion of being less than 3×10^{-5} for four consecutive data acquisition cycles. Regions I and J are system cool down and system shutdown, respectively. The total cure time for this run is 643 minutes.

Figure 3 shows the FDEMS output for the intelligent cure of PMR-15 prepreg aged 2.5 months (ICI Lot #20603S). The regions A through J correspond to those described in the

discussion of Figure 2. Region D, the Imidization Hold, requires only 11 minutes to meet the termination criterion previously described. This markedly shorter hold time here, when compared to Figure 2, indicates significant advancement of the degree of cure of the aged PMR-15. Region E determines the Crosslinking Min Viscosity temperature of 235°C, followed by a 65 minute hold in Region F. This 235°C hold temperature is identical to that seen for the expert cure of the fresh sample, indicating that the effects of incidental reaction advancement as a function of aging under freezer conditions and intrabatch/interbatch variation did not have a significant impact at this stage of the cure. The increased length of the Region F hold time from fresh to 2.5 month aged material suggests some effect of prepreg age on the slowed reaction progress at this temperature, possibly due to an increase in the percentage of volatiles remaining trapped. Finally, the Final Cure Hold seen in Region H lasts 204 minutes, with Regions I and J indicating system shut down. The total time for this intelligent cure of PMR-15 aged 2.5 months under freezer conditions is 388 minutes, 255 minutes less than the total time of the expertly cured fresh PMR-15 seen in Figure 2.

Figures 3a and 3b show the sensitivity of the $\epsilon'' \cdot \omega$ data as the polymer cures during the 235°C intermediate hold and the 320°C final hold, respectively.

Figure 4 shows the FDEMS data for the intelligent, automated sensor-model cure of PMR-15 prepreg aged seven months under freezer storage conditions (ICI Lot #10502S). The regions labelled A through J have been described.

A careful examination of the FDEMS output for the expert cure of seven month old PMR-15 seen in Figure 4 shows several things. The Region B Imidization Onset hold lasts 5 to 10 minutes longer than in the intelligent cure profiles of Figures 2 and 3, indicating significantly more moisture absorption by the prepreg material during storage. (The criteria used to determine the end of Region B for this run are that the temperature be greater than 80°C and that $((d\epsilon''/dt)/\epsilon'')$ at 25 kHz be less than 2.5×10^{-4} for four consecutive readings.) In Region D, the 250°C Imidization Hold takes only 4 minutes to meet the previously described termination requirements. Compared with the 105 minute and 11 minute hold times for Figures 2 and 3, respectively, this 4 minute hold shows the further effects of unintentional reaction advancement under freezer storage conditions over time. The Crosslinking Min Viscosity hold temperature determined in Region E is approximately 285°C, twenty degrees higher than the model generated 265°C ideal. This shows the effects of increased prepreg age, with a much higher temperature being required to soften the more reacted seven month aged part for consolidation than is required for the fresh and 2.5 month aged materials to reach the same milestone in their processing histories. Region H, the Final Cure Hold, takes only 75 minutes to reach "full cure", another indication of the prepreg's age. The total time for this intelligent cure was 290 minutes, 353 minutes shorter than the total time of the intelligently cured fresh PMR-15 shown in Figure 2.

6. CONCLUSIONS

An intelligent, automated composite cure control system has been developed and used to control the cure of PMR-15 prepreg in the autoclave and the thermal press. It consists of the synergistic coupling of the user modified DekDyne, Inc. in-situ Frequency Dependent Electromagnetic Sensing system and the Abrams Qualitative Process Automation Language logic shell. The expert system uses predictions from the Loos thermo-chemical processing model for PMR-15/graphite composite panels that followed an optimized cure profile based on FDEMS sensor output. The QPAL logic shell and the user defined PMR-15 specific knowledge base provide a flexible environment for cure process control. The expert system has shown that the optimum cure profile can vary significantly as function of resin/prepreg batch, moisture uptake, out time in part precure preparation, and incidental or intentional advancements of the degree of cure. The FDEMS-QPAL sensor-model automated cure control system responds in real time to these variations, improving the consistency of the materials' processing properties, often with

significant cost savings in processing time (18).

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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*Inquires regarding the FDEMS sensor and instrumentation should be directed to D. Kranbuehl.

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Figure 1: Values of temperature and ϵ'' multiplied by frequency for a "standard" cure of fresh PMR-15 prepreg. (Lot #10502S)

Figure 2: Values of temperature and ϵ'' multiplied by frequency for an intelligent, automated cure of fresh PMR-15 prepreg. (Lot #11769S)

Figure 3: Values of temperature and ϵ'' multiplied by frequency for an intelligent, automated cure of PMR-15 aged 2.5 months under freezer conditions. (Lot#20603S)

Figure 3a: Intermediate Hold

Figure 3b: Final Cure Hold

Figure 4: Values of temperature and ϵ'' multiplied by frequency for an intelligent, automated cure of PMR-15 prepreg aged seven months under freezer conditions. (Lot #10502S)